

ing compounds :

n-Octacosanol : Elution of the above column with petroleum ether yielded *n*-octacosanol, m.p. 83-84°, acetate, m.p. 65-66°.

β -*Sitosterol* : Further elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) gave β -sitosterol, m.p. 136°, acetate, m.p. 126°.

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Solvent Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Nickel(II) with Benzil- α -Monoxime

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A number of complexing agents have been used for the extraction and determination of nickel in different organic solvents^{1,2}. Among them oxime compounds are well known. In our laboratory benzil α -monoxime is under investigation to study the extraction behaviour of nickel. Previous use of the reagent has been reported by Paria³ and Ueda⁴ to extract platinum and cobalt. In the present communication a method is devised to extract and determine nickel spectrophotometrically in microgram levels with the reagent.

Experimental

Separating funnels (100ml) were used for the extraction purpose. Beckman DU2 Model Spectrophotometer with optically matched quartz cells (10mm path length) was used for optical density measurements.

Chloroform was distilled before use. Benzil- α -monoxime was prepared and purified in the laboratory⁵ in a good yield. A 1% acetonic solution of the oxime was used to extract nickel.

A stock solution of nickel(II) was prepared by dissolving 3.8 gm NiSO₄·7H₂O (E. Merck) in distilled water and diluted to 250ml. This was standardised gravimetrically with dimethylglyoxime⁶, contained 3.16 mg. Ni per ml. 125-fold dilution of this stock solution containing 25.3 μ g Ni per ml was used as the test solution for our routine work.

Buffer solution of different pH were prepared by standard procedures : Hydrochloric acid—potassium chloride (pH 1-2) ; acetic acid—sodium acetate (pH 3-6) , potassium hydrogen phosphate—sodium hydroxide (pH 9-11).

All other chemicals used were either chemically pure or reagent grade materials unless otherwise mentioned.

Recommended procedure for the determination of Ni(II)

An aliquot (2ml) of the test solution containing 50.6 μ g Ni was treated with 8ml buffer solution of desired pH in a separating funnel. To test the interference of the diverse ions the selected ions were added before. The volume of the aqueous phase was maintained at 10ml throughout the work. Benzil- α -monoxime in acetone (1ml, 1%) was added to the solution and kept for 10 min to ensure complete complexation. The aqueous phase was then shaken for 5 min with 10 ml chloroform. The layers were allowed to settle for 3 min and separated. The volume of the chloroform extract was made up to exactly 25 ml and the absorbance read at 360 and 400 nm against a reagent blank prepared under identical conditions. Nickel was determined accordingly from a previously prepared calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectrum

The absorption spectrum of Ni(II)-benzil- α -monoxime in chloroform shows that the chelate absorbs strongly below 310 nm and then the absorbance falls showing two absorption maxima at 360 and 400 nm. The reagent itself shows insignificant absorbances from 360 nm onwards. All the absorption measurements were carried out at 360 and 400 nm.

Effect of pH

The pH range 1-11 was studied in order to investigate the liquid-liquid extraction behaviour of the system. Extraction starts at pH 4 and becomes 100% at pH 9. In the pH range 7-10 extraction occurs to the extent of 95% or more. The extraction curve drops sharply beyond pH 10. The pH for 50% extraction are 6.3 and 10.9.

Calibration curve

Different amounts of nickel were taken and extracted as in the procedure at pH 9 and the corresponding absorbances measured in order to observe the adherence of the coloured system to Beer's law. In each case Ni was exhaustively extracted in 5 min ; the aqueous phases were always clear and colourless. The results show that Beer's law is closely obeyed at 400 nm over the concentration range of 15-90 μ g Ni per 25 ml of chloroform solution.

The safety margin of extraction is 5 min within which period nickel is quantitatively extracted in a single operation.

Molar absorptivity and sensitivity

The molar absorptivity of the complex is 1.08×10^4 and 1.02×10^4 litre mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 400 and 360 nm respectively (on the basis of nickel content) and sensitivity of the colour reaction (in terms of Sandell's definition) is 0.005 µg Ni/cm².

Stability of the colour

The absorbance of the chloroform solution of the Ni(II)-benzil- α -monoxime complex, prepared according to the general procedure at pH 9, was measured at 400 nm at elapsed times of 30 min, 1, 6, 12, 24 & 36 hours. The corresponding absorbances indicate that the colour is stable at least for 24 hours, at the end of 36 hours the absorbance decreases by about 4%. Hence it is suggested that the optical density be measured within 24 hours after the extraction.

Reagent concentration

Keeping the variables constant the concentration and amount of acetic solution of the benzil- α -monoxime was varied. It has been found that about 20-fold excess of the reagent is the requisite to operate the extraction process.

1 ml of 1% acetic solution of the reagent is sufficient to serve the purpose below which the extraction is found to be incomplete. The absorbance is more or less constant even if 2ml of 2% solution is used.

Effect of diverse ions

The following ions may be tolerated when present in amounts (µg) shown in parentheses to determine 50.6 µg Ni at pH 9: ruthenium(III) (500), palladium(II) (500), mercury(II) (1000), lead(II) (1000), lithium(I) (1000), magnesium(II) (2000), calcium(II) (2000), strontium(II) (2000), barium(II) (2000), lanthanum(III) (1500), rhodium(III) (500), platinum(IV) (500), zinc(II) (1500), cerium(III) (500), uranium(VI) (1000), tungsten(VI) (700), arsenic(III) (800).

Presence of cadmium(II), iron(III), osmium(VIII), copper(II), beryllium(II), zirconium(IV), chromium(II), aluminium(III), thorium(IV) results incomplete extraction. Manganese(II), cobalt(II), vanadium(V) impart high results.

Among the anions tested, chloride (3000), bromide (1000), thiocyanate (2500), iodide(500), thiosulphate (1000), oxalate (2000), borate(4000), tartrate (4000), phosphate (4000) do not interfere in the extraction procedure. However EDTA and fluoride interfere rather seriously.

Precision and accuracy

In six such runs with 50.6 µg Ni(II), the relative mean deviation in the absorbances found, was $\pm 1.7\%$. Different amounts of Ni(II) were taken and determined by the recommended procedure. The results are accurate to within $\pm 2.4\%$.

Thus the process is rapid, simple and a fairly satisfactory one requiring only 20-25 min for each run.

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Chalcones XXIII : Studies on Potential Germicides Derived from Substituted Methyl Aryl Ketones.

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PPROMISING usefulness of chalcones and their analogues as bactericides, ^{2,6, 23, 24}, insecticides, ^{11, 12, 20} germicides, ^{7-9, 16-19}, cardiovascular, sedative ^{1, 2, 5}, antifertility¹⁰, etc. agents have been reported. Wilson and coworkers¹⁰ used these compounds to protect adrenaline from destruction. Hydroxy chalcones possess¹⁵ increased antimicrobial activity without damaging the host tissues. Gowan and Brian also observed²¹ fungistatic action of heterocyclic chalcones on *A. niger* at low concen-